

Supplemental Material of *Delivering Green Persuasion Strategies with a Conversational Agent: a Pilot Study*

A. Appendix of Research Variables

This appendix contains the statements proposed in the questionnaire for users to evaluate: *self-efficacy*, *action effect*, and *future intentions*, assessed with a 7-point Likert scale (1-Strongly disagree / 7-Strongly agree). The authors would like to acknowledge the contribution of Andrea Bernardino, Giulio Faccenda, and Simona Sacchi, (University of Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy) in creating the following metrics for the questionnaire.

A.1. Self-efficacy

- I am able to minimize unnecessary electricity consumption in my home
- I am able to achieve most of the energy-saving goals I have set for myself
- The choice to reduce energy consumption in my home is out of my control

A.2. Action Effect

- The choice to reduce energy consumption will contribute to combating climate change
- My commitment to reducing energy consumption is able to safeguard the environment
- By reducing my energy consumption, I can contribute to reducing global emissions

A.3. Future Intentions

- Turn off the lights when leaving a room
- Leave the air conditioner on even when you leave the house
- Take into account energy efficiency claims in case you have to buy an appliance
- Set the 'Eco' program when using the dishwasher
- Use free apps that allow you to track your daily energy consumption

- Start a high-temperature wash when the washing machine is not yet fully loaded
- Leave the TV on even when you are busy with other chores
- Leaving the fridge door open while you decide what to cook
- Turn off electronic devices when not in use and avoid leaving them on standby
- Set the washing machine washing temperature to 30°C or less
- Turn off your computer monitor when you are not working

B. Appendix of Procedure

The hypothetical scenario stated:

It's 1 p.m. on a Sunday in early August, it's a very muggy day (33°C), and you're home with the air conditioner on full blast to try to cool the house. You've finished lunch, cleared the table, loaded the dishwasher, and – since the dishes and pans have some crusty dirt on them – you select the intensive program (70°C, duration: 3h). Then you lie down on the couch to relax and turn on the TV. Suddenly you remember that you have to wash your laundry, so you decide to load the washing machine; to ensure better hygiene, you select the "Cotton" program (90°C, duration: 3h).

After having activated these appliances, you receive a notification from your Ecobot.

In addition, they were introduced to a generic task asking to retrieve information about home consumption to follow in the next phase:

You have just received a notification from your Ecobot. We ask you to read it and chat with the agent to learn more about your home's consumption and its appliances. Feel free to chat as you see fit.

C. Appendix of Results

Comprehensive and detailed view of the results in Table 1.

D. Appendix with Examples of Conversations

In this appendix, we report chats between users and *Ecobot* extracted by the logs of the experimentation.

Example 1. Example of a conversation in the *Feedback* condition.

User: how I could reduce the consumption of my household appliances

Bot: The appliances that have consumed the most are: air conditioner with 80 kWh, refrigerator with 70 kWh, boiler with 65 kWh. Instead, the appliances that have consumed the least are microwaves with 5 kWh, induction hobs with 20 kWh, television with 25 kWh. If you want to have a suggestion on how to consume less energy, write 'give me a suggestion for air conditioning'.

User: give me a suggestion for air conditioning

Bot: Here's a tip for you: Make sure you have all the windows closed tightly, otherwise the air conditioner won't work at its best.

User: there is better I can do

Bot: Hello! My name is EcoBot, and I will help you save energy. I can give you tips and trivia (try saying, 'give me a trivia about the television' or 'give me a tip for the air conditioner'), and monitor your consumption (try 'which appliances should I use less?' or 'how much do I spend for the boiler every month?').

User: give me another suggestion for the air conditioner

Bot: Here's a tip for you: The installation position of the air conditioner is very important: the ideal situation is to install it in a shady position in the house.

User: give me a suggestion for the washing machine

Bot: Here's a tip for you: Always check if the washing machine is fully loaded before starting it. Remember that starting a washing machine with no full load wastes energy.

User: give me a curiosity about television

Bot: Here's a curiosity for you: On average, a modern television consumes 26 kWh in standby over the course of a year.

User: how much the dishwasher consumes

Bot: This month, you have already consumed 35kWh per dishwasher. On average, however, you consume 40kWh per month for dishwashers.

User: how can I reduce my consumption even further

Bot: Here's a tip for you: Choose a dishwasher of the right size, to maximize the use of water and energy.

User: best to use the microwave or oven for cooking

Bot: This month, you have already spent €11 per oven. On average, however, you spend €14 per month per oven.

User: how much I spend on the microwave

Bot: This month, you've already spent €1 on a microwave. On average, however, you spend €3 a month on a microwave.

Example 2. Example of a conversation in the *Combined* condition.

User: how can I reduce consumption

Bot: For which device? If you want, you can also tell me 'all devices'.

User: all devices

Bot: Here's a tip for you: Choose low-consumption appliances: they are class A+++, A++, or A+.

User: how many degrees the washing machine at to reduce consumption

Bot: Here's a tip for you: Often, the 'Cotton' program of your washing machine is not really necessary. Next time, try to think about what you're washing and choose the most suitable and least energy-intensive program.

User: how many degrees is the air conditioner at

Bot: I'm sorry, I wish I could help you, but unfortunately, I can't turn on, turn off, or check the status of an appliance directly, nor know its details. I can only monitor them over time to show you your consumption and give you suggestions.

User: to save money, I have to turn off some appliances

Table 1: Descriptive Results of the Scores for each Experimental Condition

	Condition	FI	SE	AE	NEP	PSI	SUS	N. Int	T. Int (s)
Mean	Complete	4.49	4.52	5.19	5.16	4.18	82.8	81.4	1048
	Feedback	4.51	5.02	5.18	4.95	3.66	84.1	55.1	701
Standard Deviation	Complete	0.587	0.748	1.72	0.661	0.358	11.7	33.7	338
	Feedback	0.621	1.04	1.36	0.881	0.544	8.41	32.2	325
Median	Complete	4.55	4.83	5.67	5.23	4.25	86.4	90.0	1057
	Feedback	4.45	5.33	5.33	5.20	3.75	87.1	43	630
Minimum	Complete	3.36	3.00	1.33	3.67	3.33	54.3	21	600
	Feedback	3.27	3.33	2.33	3.60	2.92	64.3	17	213
Maximum	Complete	5.36	5.33	7.00	6.07	4.83	100	127	1593
	Feedback	5.55	6.67	7.00	6.13	4.50	92.9	133	1496

FI=future intentions, SE=self-efficacy, AE=action effect, N. Int= interaction number, T. Int=interaction time (in seconds)

Bot: I have set a goal for dishwashers: usually, you consume 40 kWh per month. I set the goal to 36 kWh per month. You can change it at any time if you want.

User: give me a dishwasher suggestion

Bot: Here's a tip for you: If you use an energy-saving program in your dishwasher, the dishes are washed at a lower temperature, around 50°C, using about three liters less water than in the normal cycle.

User: what you can do

Bot: Hello! My name is EcoBot, and I will help you save energy every month. You can set a consumption target for a specific appliance (for example: try saying 'set a target for television', to help you use your TV less each month), receive a suggestion or a curiosity to save energy ('give me a tip for the television', 'give me a tip for the boiler') or check if you are consuming more or less than your region ('Am I consuming more or less than the average in my region?') or others EcoBot users for a certain appliance ('Am I consuming more than average for television?'). Try writing something!

User: I'm consuming more than the average for television

Bot: Usually, you consume more than the average of other television users. Indeed, 25 kWh is your average consumption in a month, while the average for other users is 20 kWh.

User: give me a trivia about the boiler

Bot: Here's a curiosity for you: The latest generation boiler allows you to save 30%

User: how much my boiler consumes

Bot: This month, you have already consumed 55kWh per boiler. On average, however, you consume 65kWh per month per boiler.

User: set a target for television

Bot: I have set a goal for television: I usually consume 25 kWh per month. I set the goal to 23 kWh per month. You can change it at any time if you want.

User: edit

Bot: Ok! Is the televised goal too difficult or too easy?

User: too difficult

Bot: Ok! I decrease the difficulty of the objective by 10

User: thank you

Bot: You're welcome. It's a pleasure helping you!

Example 2. Another example of a conversation in the *Combined* condition.

[... chats on feedback]

User: how much the tele consumes

Bot: In which Italian region area do you live? I will remember it in the future!

User: lombardy

Bot: You are consuming, on average, 196 kWh more than the average in Lombardy! Want to set a goal for the whole house to try to use less energy?

User: ok

User: set a goal for the whole house

Bot: I set a goal for my home: usually, you consume 400 kWh per month. I set the goal to 360 kWh per month. You can change it at any time if you want.

[... chats on feedback and goal-setting]